

The Study of the Effect of Higher Secondary School Teachers' Teaching Commitment on the Teaching Aptitude of the School Teachers of the Ahmedabad City

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ABSTRACT: This paper focuses on the study of the effect of higher secondary school teachers' teaching commitment on their teaching aptitude among school teachers in Ahmedabad City. The main objective of the study was to know the effect of teacher commitment, gender and experience on their teaching aptitude. A random sampling technique was used to collect samples, and a standardized tool of Modi was used to assess teacher commitment and teaching aptitude. The T-Test was conducted to analyze the main effects of teacher commitment, gender and experience on their effects on teaching aptitude. The population of the study consisted of higher secondary school teachers in Ahmedabad City. The findings reveal that there is no significant difference between teacher commitment, gender and experience in teaching aptitude.

KEYWORDS: higher secondary school teacher, teaching commitment, teaching aptitude

Introduction

Teachers worldwide are encouraged to improve the efficacy of their teaching and learning situations. Teachers are the primary source of positive influence for students. Teachers' interactions in and out of the classroom influence students' values, both positive and negative. The teacher is responsible for identifying areas of weakness in the student's studies and identifying obstacles to achieving the set objective. The teacher's role is to motivate and set goals for pupils, allowing them to identify their strengths and abilities. A teacher who understands multi-intelligence may effectively improve each student's dominated ability. Achieving the goal of being an 'excellent teacher' requires commitment. The Government of India introduced the Teachers' Aptitude Test in 2011 to improve the standard of teaching in higher secondary schools.

The teacher's topic expertise and commitment to teaching are both high. It is believed that a committed teacher has a greater impact on teaching. The teacher's teaching will be more successful as the level of dedication increases. The teacher's aptitude may fluctuate for various reasons. The question is whether such teachers are committed to teaching. Furthermore, it is important to determine whether there is a difference in low, medium, and high dedication in terms of teaching aptitude. With all of these considerations in mind, the study was decided.

Research Review

By reviewing the previous research, it is found that the study of the effect of teaching commitment on the teaching aptitude has not been done on the higher secondary school teachers were as the effect of leadership and the effect of the salary on the teaching aptitude and commitment was studied.

Reviewing the work of Kaur and Singh (2012), Gupta and Gehlawat (2013), Vaghela (2014), Azer (2014), Rupa and Lakshmi (2015), Darandale (2017) it was found that there is no difference between the teaching aptitude of male and female secondary teachers. On the other side, by reviewing the work of Gondhi (2015) and Mitra (2017) it was found that female and male teachers have different teaching aptitude.

Rationale of the study

A critical analysis of the findings reveals a state of dispute on the teaching aptitude and commitment of male and female teachers. According to Gupta and Ghelawat (2013) and Vaghela (2014), teachers with more than 10 years of teaching experience are more committed compared to those with less than 10 years of experience. According to Rupa and Lakshmi (2015) and Azer (2014), more experienced teachers tend to have less commitment. On the other hand, according to Gupta and Gehlawat (2013), gender has no impact on a teacher's commitment. However, Kaur and Singh (2012) discovered that female teachers were more committed than male teachers. According to Gondhi (2015) and Mitra (2017), female and male teachers have different teaching aptitudes. The controversy surrounding the relationship between gender and experience will be addressed by conducting a gender-wise and experience-wise comparison of teaching aptitude among teachers.

Variables

The following are the variables of the present study:

(1) *Independent Variable*

1. Teacher Commitment

- i. High
- ii. Medium
- iii. Low

2. Gender

- i. Male
- ii. Female

3. Experience

- i. More than 5 years
- ii. Less than 5 years

(2) *Dependent Variable*: Higher Secondary Section

Objective of the study

The present study has the following objectives:

1. To study the teaching aptitude of the teachers.
2. To study the commitment of the teachers.
3. To study the teaching aptitudes of male and female teachers.
4. To study the commitment of male and female teachers.
5. To study the teaching aptitudes teachers having more than 5 years of experience and having less than 5 years of experience.

Hypotheses of the study

In the present study, we propose the following hypotheses:

- H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teaching Aptitude of teachers having high and medium commitment level.
- H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teaching Aptitude of teachers having medium and low commitment level.
- H₀₃ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teaching Aptitude of teachers having high and low commitment level.
- H₀₄ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teaching Aptitude of male and female teachers.

- H₀₅ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teachers' Commitment of male and female teachers.
- H₀₆ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teaching aptitude of male teachers having more than 5 years of experience and having less than 5 years of experience.
- H₀₇ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teaching aptitude of female teachers having more than 5 years of experience and female teaching having less than 5 years of experience.
- H₀₈ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teaching aptitude of male and female teachers having more than 5 years of experience.
- H₀₉ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teaching aptitude of male and female teachers having less than 5 years of experience.

Limitation of the study

1. The study researcher used a self-constructed research tool.
2. The study was limited to higher secondary school teachers in Ahmedabad city.
3. The sample was selected among the teachers of higher secondary schools from East and West zones of Ahmedabad city.

Method of study

A survey method was adopted to know the effect of the higher secondary school teachers teaching commitment on their teaching aptitude of the School Teachers in the Ahmedabad City.

Statistical method

For statistical analysis of the obtained data, it has been decided to test whether the difference between the mean scores obtained by the teachers is significant or not by using the 't' test.

Population of the study

The higher secondary school teachers were selected from both government, grant in aid, and private schools. Sampling was done by dividing the city of Ahmedabad into two zones as follows: East and West zones.

Sample of the study

In the present study, a total 1000 higher secondary school teachers were selected according to the stratified random method, in which a total of 500 males and 500 females were included.

Tool of the study

A self-developed tool was used.

Data collection and analysis

The data was collected through a physical form of the tool. The tool was sent physically according to zones to the various teachers by contacting the school personally. The tool's first page included the correct instructions that teachers were to follow while filling it out.

- H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teaching Aptitude of teachers having high and medium commitment level.

Table 1: T-test Scores of High commitment and Medium Commitment levels in Teacher Commitment Test

Level of Commitment	N	T-test
High	362	0.75
Medium	358	

On the basis of the T-Scores of aptitude obtained from the high and medium commitment level of higher secondary school teachers of Ahmedabad city in Teacher Aptitude Test is 0.75, as shown in the Table 1, which is less than $t_{tab} = 1.96$, that is required for significant mean difference at .05 levels of significance for $df = 720$. No significant difference was found in the teaching aptitude of higher secondary school teachers who had high and medium commitment levels. So, null hypothesis was not rejected.

H_{02} There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teaching Aptitude of teachers having medium and low commitment level.

Table 2: T-test Scores of Medium commitment and Low Commitment levels in Teacher Commitment Test

Level of Commitment	N	T-test
Medium	358	0.47
Low	280	

On the basis of the T-Scores of aptitude obtained from the medium and low commitment level of higher secondary school teachers of Ahmedabad city in Teacher Aptitude Test is 0.47 as shown in the Table 2. This is less than $t_{tab} = 1.96$ that is required for significant mean difference at .05 levels of significance for $df = 638$. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of higher secondary school teachers who had medium and low commitment levels. So, null hypothesis was not rejected.

H_{03} There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teaching Aptitude of teachers having high and low commitment level.

Table 3: T-test Scores of High commitment and Low Commitment levels in Teacher Commitment Test

Level of Commitment	N	T-test
High	362	0.25
Low	280	

On the basis of the T-Scores of aptitude obtained from the high and low commitment level of higher secondary school teachers of Ahmedabad city in Teacher Aptitude Test is 0.25 as shown in the Table 3. This is less than $t_{tab} = 1.96$ that is required for significant mean difference at .05 levels of significance for $df = 642$. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of higher secondary school teachers who had high and low commitment levels. So, null hypothesis was not rejected.

H_{04} There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teaching Aptitude of male and female teachers.

Table 4: T-Test Scores of male and female teacher in teaching aptitude of test

Gender	N	T-test
Male	464	0.26
Female	536	

On the basis of the T-Scores of aptitudes obtained from the male and female teachers of higher secondary schools teachers of Ahmedabad city in Teacher Aptitude Test is 0.26 as shown in the Table 4, which is less than $t_{tab} = 1.96$ that is required for significant mean difference at .05 levels of significance for $df = 1000$. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of male and female higher secondary school teachers of Ahmedabad City. So, null hypothesis was not rejected.

H_{05} There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Teachers' Commitment of male and female teachers.

Table 5: T-Test Scores of male and female teachers in teaching commitment test

Gender	N	T-test
Male	464	0.65
Female	536	

On the basis of the T-Scores of aptitudes obtained from the male and female teachers of higher secondary schools teachers of Ahmedabad city in Teacher Aptitude Test is 0.65 as shown in the Table 5, which is less than $t_{tab} = 1.96$ that is required for significant mean difference at .05 levels of significance for $df = 1000$. There was no significant difference found in the commitment of male and female higher secondary school teachers of Ahmedabad City. So, null hypothesis was not rejected.

H_{06} There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teaching aptitude of male teachers having more than 5 years of experience and having less than 5 years of experience.

Table 6: T-Scores of male teachers having more than 5 years experience and less than 5 years experience in teaching aptitude test

Experience	N	T-test
More than 5 years	300	0.21
Less than 5 years	164	

On the basis of the T-Scores of aptitudes obtained from the male teachers of higher secondary schools teachers of Ahmedabad City in Teacher Aptitude Test is 0.21 as shown in the Table 6, which is less than $t_{tab} = 1.96$ that is required for significant mean difference at .05 levels of significance for $df = 464$. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of male teachers having more than 5 years of experience and less than 5 years of experience. So, null hypothesis was not rejected.

H_{07} There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teaching aptitude of female teachers having more than 5 years of experience and female teaching having less than 5 years of experience.

Table 7: T-Scores of female teachers having more than 5 years experience and less than 5 years experience in teaching aptitude test

Experience	N	T-test
More than 5 years	242	0.06
Less than 5 years	294	

On the basis of the T-Scores of aptitudes obtained from the female teachers of higher secondary schools teachers of Ahmedabad City in Teacher Aptitude Test is 0.06 as shown in the Table 7, which is less than $t_{tab} = 1.96$ that is required for significant mean difference at .05 levels of significance for $df = 536$. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of female teachers having more than 5 years of experience and less than 5 years of experience. So, null hypothesis was not rejected.

H_{08} There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teaching aptitude of male and female teachers having more than 5 years of experience.

Table 8: T-Scores of male and female teachers with more than 5 years' of experience in teaching aptitude test

More than 5 years	N	T-test
Male	300	0.13
Female	242	

On the basis of the T-Scores of aptitudes obtained from the male and female teachers of higher secondary school teachers of Ahmedabad city in Teacher Aptitude Test is 0.13 as shown in the Table 8, which is less than $t_{tab} = 1.96$ that is required for significant mean difference at .05 levels of significance for $df = 542$. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of both male and female teachers with more than 5 years of experience. So, Null hypothesis was not rejected.

H_{09} There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teaching aptitude of male and female teachers having less than 5 years of experience.

Table 9: T-Scores of male and female teachers with Less than 5 years' of experience in teaching aptitude test

Less than 5 years	N	T-test
Male	164	0.29
Female	294	

On the basis of the T-Scores of aptitudes obtained from the male and female teachers of higher secondary school teachers of Ahmedabad city in Teacher Aptitude Test is 0.29 as shown in the Table 9, which is less than $t_{tab} = 1.96$ that is required for significant mean difference at .05 levels of significance for $df = 458$. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of both male and female teachers with less than 5 years of experience. So, Null hypothesis was not rejected.

Findings of research

The findings of the study are as under:

1. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of higher secondary school teachers who had high and medium commitment levels.
2. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of higher secondary school teachers who had medium and low commitment levels.
3. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of higher secondary school teachers who had high and low commitment levels.
4. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of male and female higher secondary school teachers of Ahmedabad City.
5. There was no significant difference found in the commitment of male and female higher secondary school teachers of Ahmedabad City.

6. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of male teachers having more than 5 years of experience and less than 5 years of experience.
7. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of female teachers having more than 5 years of experience and less than 5 years of experience.
8. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of both male and female teachers with more than 5 years of experience.
9. There was no significant difference found in the teaching aptitude of both male and female teachers with less than 5 years of experience.

Implication of the study

1. Regular in-service training is recommended for higher secondary school teacher to improve their teaching aptitude.
2. Teachers in higher secondary schools should conduct regular observations to enhance their teaching aptitude.
3. Higher secondary school teachers can improve their teaching aptitude by receiving regular feedback on their own sessions.
4. Teachers in higher secondary school should establish clear teaching objectives.
5. Teachers at higher secondary school should have subject knowledge.
6. Higher secondary school teachers should develop a well-thought-out lesson plan for the session.
7. Teachers of higher secondary schools should gather information regarding the latest teaching methods and techniques.
8. In order to improve their ability to teach, higher secondary school teachers should practise effective classroom interaction techniques.

Conclusion

In the present study important things like objectives, hypothesis, research process and important findings are included in this paper according to the findings show that there is no significant difference between teacher commitment, gender and experience in teaching competence.

References

- Azer, Eskandaricharati. 2014. "Organizational Commitment Of Secondary School Teachers In Relation To Leadership Preference Organizational Climate And Type Of School." Doctoral Thesis, retrieved on March 12 from Shodhganga@inlibnet.
- Darandale, Jagannath Bahirath. 2017. "A Comparative Study of the Relationship Between Organizational Commitment and Stress among Primary and Secondary School Teachers." Doctoral Thesis, retrieved on March 27 from <https://shodhganga.inlibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/266033>.
- Gupta, Madhu and Manju Gehlawat. 2013. "Examining The Relationship Among Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction And Work Motivation Of Secondary School Teachers." Doctoral Thesis, retrieved on February 9 from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/71446>.
- Kaur, Gurdeep and Venita Singh. 2012. "Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers in Relation to Leadership Preference, Organizational Climate and Type of School." Doctoral Thesis, retrieved on February 9 from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/79924>.
- Mitra, Sudakshina. 2017. "A Study on the Academic Success of Student- Teachers in Relation to Teaching Aptitude and Attitude towards Teaching Profession. Doctoral Thesis, retrieved on March 3.
- Patel, R.S. 2010. *Research Methodology*. Ahmedabad: Jay Publication.
- Rupa, N. T. and Lakshmi N. 2015. "A Study Of Teachers Commitment In Relation To Their Heads Leadership Effectiveness And Organizational Culture At Secondary School. Doctoral Thesis, retrieved on February 13 from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/306819>.
- Shukla, Satishprakash. 2018. *Research Methodology and Statistics*. Ahmedabad: Rishit Publications.
- Vaghela, Naresh. 2014. "Study Of Work Motivation And Commitment Of Female Teachers In Relation To Types Of Organization Experience And AcademicLevel. Doctoral Thesis, retrieved on February 21 from Shodhganga@inlibnet.